

Studies on the Formation of Double Bromides of Antimony Tribromide with other Metal Bromides

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The formation of double bromides of antimony with the bromides of Na, K, NH_4 , Cu(I), Cu (II), Ca, Sr, Ba, Cd, Hg(I), Hg(II), Sn, and Fe (III) has been studied. The compounds have been isolated, their properties studied, and structures discussed.

Mellor¹ has described the formation of some double bromides of antimony with other metal bromides. Isbekow², Pushin and Makuc³, and Eingorn⁴ postulated the formation of complexes from the melting point curves of the systems $\text{SbBr}_3\text{—AlBr}_3$, $\text{SbBr}_3\text{—PBr}_3$ and $\text{SbBr}_3\text{—SnBr}_2$ and $\text{SbBr}_3\text{—TiBr}_4$ respectively. Bournazos⁵ prepared $\text{K}_2\text{Sb}_3\text{Br}_6\text{I}_2$ by refluxing a mixture of KI, SbBr_3 , and an acid on a water bath and extended his work to the study of several similar compounds. Petzold⁶ found that the complex bromides of Sb(V) were formed by adding bromine to a solution of SbBr_3 and other metal bromide. Elliott⁷ and Jenson⁸ found $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SbBr}_6$ and Rb_2SbBr_6 to be diamagnetic. Turco and Mazzoni⁹ prepared $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SbBr}_6$ by the application of radioactive antimony.

A general survey of the literature shows that the double bromides of antimony have been studied only in aqueous medium. The present investigation was undertaken with a view to studying the formation of double bromides of antimony in organic solvents.

EXPERIMENTAL

The chemicals used were of Merck's or B. D. H. 'pure' quality and solvents were dehydrated and redistilled.

Saturated solution of antimony tribromide was taken in ethyl acetate and it was mixed with a saturated solution of other bromides in the same solvent, when double halides separated on shaking. But in some cases, the compound was separated by adding a second solvent, [e.g. Na and K compounds by benzene and Fe (III) by ether]. Before adding the second solvent, the reaction mixture was kept for 48 hr. with frequent shaking to attain the equilibrium.

1. "Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", Part IX, p. 496.
2. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1925, 143, 80.
3. *Ibid.*, 1938, 237, 177.
4. *Ukrain Khim. Zhur.*, 1950, 16, No. 4, 414.
5. *Praktika*, 1932, 7, 227.
6. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1933, 215, 1022.
7. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1934, 2, 298.
8. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1937, 232, 193.
9. *Ann. Chim. Rome*, 1953, 43, 853.

Attempts were made to prepare analogous compounds with Li, Mg, and Pb bromides, but no compound could be isolated in these cases owing to the solubility of the complexes in organic solvents in the first two cases and to insolubility of $PbBr_2$ in organic solvents in the last case.

In the case of alkaline earths, when the two solutions were mixed, the heavy liquid separating was isolated by means of a separating funnel, washed several times with ethyl acetate, and dried in a vacuum desiccator.

Antimony and mercury were estimated as sulphides, barium and strontium as sulphates, cadmium as pyrophosphate, tin and iron as oxides, copper iodometrically, calcium by converting it into oxalate and titrating it against potassium permanganate, and bromine by Piria and Schiff's method. Sodium, potassium, ammonium, and solvent molecules were estimated by difference.

TABLE I

Bro- mides.	Colour.	% Antimony.		% Other metal.		% Bromine.		% Solvent.		Probable formula.
		Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	
$NaBr$	White	21.03	21.43	8.03	8.10	70.94	70.44	..	..	$Na_2[SbBr_3]$
KBr	Pale yellow	20.01	20.29	13.10	13.01	66.89	66.69	..	..	$K_2[SbBr_3]$
NH_4Br	Yellow	21.74	21.82	6.02	6.45	72.24	71.71	..	..	$(NH_4)_2[SbBr_3]$
Cu_2Br_2	Brown	18.92	18.74	18.90	19.54	60.54	61.49	..	..	$Cu_2[SbBr_3]$
$CuBr_2$	Buff	20.60	20.56	10.73	10.88	69.01	68.55	..	..	$Cu[SbBr_3]$
$CaBr_2$	Orange- red	9.60	9.02	3.19	3.16	31.80	31.62	55.41	55.65	$Ca[SbBr_3].8CH_3CO_2Et$
$SrBr_2$	Red	14.28	13.94	9.17	10.06	45.78	45.82	30.77	30.18	$Sr[SbBr_3].3(CH_3CO_2Et)$
$BaBr_2$	Red	9.01	9.54	11.10	10.77	30.75	31.38	49.14	48.32	$Ba[SbBr_3].7CH_3CO_2Et$
$CdBr_2$	Brown	19.49	19.20	16.85	17.67	63.83	63.13	..	..	$Cd[SbBr_3]$
Hg_2Br_2	Dirty white	13.30	13.18	43.08	43.37	43.07	43.35	..	..	$Hg_2[SbBr_3]$
$HgBr_2$	Ash	16.63	16.65	28.05	27.77	53.09	53.30	..	..	$Hg[SbBr_3]$
$SnBr_2$	Brown	19.23	19.00	18.03	18.54	62.05	62.46	..	..	$Sn[SbBr_3]$
$FeBr_3$	Brown	18.78	18.49	8.32	8.51	72.54	72.07	..	..	$Fe[SbBr_3]$

General Properties.—The compounds are coloured, crystalline powders except those of alkaline earth metals. The solvent molecules associated with them were removed by heating at 80-85° except in the case of calcium. The compounds are soluble in mineral acids. Generally these are insoluble in ethanol and benzene. All the compounds are insoluble in ethyl acetate except sodium, potassium, and iron compounds. These are hygroscopic, are easily hydrolysed by water, and decompose on heating.

DISCUSSION

The properties of the compounds studied reveal that these are not penetration complexes, but may be classed as normal complexes which are reversibly dissociated into their constituents either in the solid phase or in solution, in which therefore the linking of the constituents is but loose.

The compounds are fairly stable in dry atmosphere, but decompose when they come in contact with water. The fact that some bromides, which are insoluble in organic solvents, dissolve on adding SbBr_3 solution further supports the assumption that the complex compounds are being formed. These may be represented as:

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